

USE OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN CONDUCTING EDUCATIONAL LESSONS

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Abstract. In this article, thoughts are discussed about the current tasks before the technology science of general secondary schools, psychological, pedagogical and technical-technological aspects of the educational process.

Key words. project, creativity, creative thinking, ability, creative abilities.

In the currently adopted presidential decisions on education, special attention is paid to the training of modern-thinking pedagogical personnel, the use of advanced pedagogical and information-communication technologies, as well as electronic educational resources and multimedia presentations in the educational process. In this regard, it is one of the urgent tasks of pedagogues today to learn how to conduct training effectively, interestingly, meaningfully and at the level of the times.

During the development of pedagogical technologies and their entry into the educational process, as well as the rapid exchange and improvement of information technologies, an opportunity is created for each person to strengthen their professional training and skills.

"Man, his all-round harmonious development and well-being, creation of conditions for realization of personal interests, change of outdated patterns of thinking and social behavior are the main goal and driving force of the reforms implemented in the republic. "Formation of an excellent system of personnel training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal values, on the basis of the achievements of modern culture, economy, science and technology, is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan," it was stated. In recent years, a lot of necessary work has been done and is still being done to improve the national education and training system in our country. The educational system was improved, a number of new types of educational institutions were established, curricula, curricula, and educational standards were created for them. The task at Gal is to widely introduce the achievements of world pedagogy and new pedagogical technologies into the content of education in order to implement these great works.

Today's task of education is to teach students to be able to work independently in the conditions of an information-educational environment that is increasing day by day, to use the flow of information wisely, to think critically, to express one's opinion, to be able to evaluate oneself.

Teachers of educational institutions should form highly qualified specialists - citizens of Uzbekistan who are capable of an active life, who will correctly aim in the modern system of values of our society.

The task before the teachers of educational institutions is to prepare the young generation who flexibly adapts to the changes taking place in the world, affects life situations with a state of activity, thinks critically, is capable of understanding other people and cooperation, increases personal responsibility for his education, self-improvement and career growth.

In particular, games aimed at imagining historical reality and active games occupy a special place in the emotional-intellectual development of students.

Active games are modeled in relation to a specific reality. In the process of such games, students are mobilized to perform specific tasks. In them, students' behavior, boldness, solidarity are shown in two forms.

The use of such pedagogical technologies is focused on friendly relations and cooperation. Therefore, the general content and organizational program of pedagogical technologies should be based on the embodiment of cooperative activities of pupils or students.

For example: Problem-discussion game. In this, all the students' actions are united around the problem or issue under discussion. During the game, the students argue, the teacher interferes in this process as little as possible. The teacher puts problems and questions to the students, assigns tasks to them. Students will solve problems during this game. The solutions to the problems and issues presented to them will not be known in advance. At the end of the game, students can make some comments. At this point, students' actions in developing and solving problems are important.

In the formation of professional qualification education, students use various methods of professional diagnosis: observation, analysis of students' practical actions, skills, beliefs, filling out questionnaires, conversations, interviews, pedagogical experiments, and help students to determine their professional goals.

In addition, students' imagination skills are also important. Technical means of modern teaching; computers, electronic whiteboards, video projectors, etc., ensure the easy learning of the lesson process by the students, provide an opportunity for the students to easily understand and imagine the processes.

In this case, training can be conducted using a number of methods, such as conferences, brainstorming, trips, working in small groups. For example, if lessons related to imparting new knowledge are conducted using methods such

as conferences, working in small groups, students' activity in the lesson increases. Laboratory or practical training can be carried out by traveling, working in small groups, relay, interactive, cluster, KVN and other methods.

It is good to show films and shows related to the subjects of the lesson processes. For this purpose, educational materials posted on "Zionet", "edu.uz", "uzedu.uz" and other educational sites can be used effectively.

At this point, it is also appropriate to talk about distance education. Speaking about the pedagogical technologies of distance education, it is necessary to organize the educational process in such a way that the student can apply the necessary fundamental knowledge to solve practical problems with his partners, make observations using Internet technologies, and have the opportunity to evaluate his own knowledge levels and achievements. create opportunities for him to correct his activities.

If the lessons are organized based on such methods, the lesson will be fun, interesting and meaningful, students will not get bored in such a lesson; interest in classes increases, a strong desire to participate is created, an opportunity to show oneself in all ways is created.

As a result, during the lesson, students become active, each student thinks and works, they respect each other's views and opinions and fill them with their own thoughts. Characteristics such as interpersonal social relations and mutual support arise among students.

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